

Molecular Dynamics Software Interoperability Workshop Report

Nov 3-5, 2018 | New York

The Molecular Dynamics Software Interoperability workshop was held on Nov 3-5 in Brooklyn, New York. The workshop started in the afternoon on Nov 3 (Sunday) and ended in the early afternoon on Nov 5 (Tuesday). The total number of participants was 35, where one participant joined the meeting remotely. The venue, accommodation and catering for the event were provided by The Hoxton hotel. The workshop was primarily funded by the MolSSI with additional support from the Chodera lab and Piquemal lab for equipment rental and conference dinner, respectively. More detailed breakdown of the workshop costs and the full list of attendees is provided below:

- [Participants](#) - the full list of attendees with their affiliations and contact details;
- [Expenses](#) - workshop expenditures with receipts;
- [Photos](#) - a selection of conference photos.

Workshop format

This workshop was focused on interoperability of molecular dynamics software, calculation reproducibility and best practices for research code and data sharing. The workshop was divided in 4 sessions listed below. Each session started with several talks trying to provide some context for each topic by sharing presenters' insights in the current state of the matter and what are the biggest challenges for addressing problems discussed in each session. This series of talks was followed by all-hands discussions, which aimed to answer the following questions and come up with a list of actionable items:

- What can be done in the near future to fix some problems, i.e. within a year?
- What could be a long term solution?
- How could we achieve it?

A brief summary of each session with links to meeting notes and session recordings are provided below. The meeting participants also live tweeted during the event using [#MDSI2019](#) hashtag. All sessions were recorded and meeting notes were taken during discussions. Please note that the audio quality of the provided recordings varies, depending on the distance of the speaker from the microphone. All materials produced during this workshop have been shared in the publicly available [Google drive](#). These files will be uploaded to YouTube and Zenodo for DOI assignment, more permanent record keeping and easier information sharing.

Workshop sessions

1. [Storing, analyzing and visualizing](#)

Detailed protocol description and result reporting is an essential part of scientific communication, and the value of sharing data and code has been emphasized across different scientific disciplines in recent years. Despite increased interest among researchers to engage in more open practices, the adoption has been slow. For example, molecular dynamics datasets are growing, which makes storing, sharing, analyzing and visualising increasingly challenging, but the adequate infrastructure support is either lagging or it has limited availability (institutional, geographical, topical, etc). Different requirements and practices around data and code management across different labs and institutions add an additional layer of difficulty when it comes to development of a systematic sharing approach. This results with an additional burden for scientists who are making all their research output openly available, especially when this

practice is still poorly rewarded. Provision of raw data and code used to produce results in the submitted manuscripts is rarely a mandatory requirement in most of the traditional journals.

Discussion in this session focused on what could be done to encourage, improve and support sharing of simulation data and protocols in an accurate, efficient and systematic way under current conditions, and how this could be improved over time. Creating best practice guidelines for data sharing was deemed as a good first step on the path to more elaborate solutions or platform building. This would include defining a minimal dataset that should be provided with every MD publication, for example, relevant input files and a few snapshots of the simulated system. Editors and reviewers in journals could request this data and help promote this data sharing as a standard practice in the field. Building a specialized infrastructure for sharing MD data has been considered and its value could potentially be high for both research and educational purposes, but a long term sustainability of such infrastructure has been recognized as a major challenge in the current funding climate.

- **Speakers:** Johanna Tiemann (chair), Karissa Sanbonmatsu, Anna Lappala, Matthieu Montes, Mauricio Carrillo Tripp, Zoe Cournia
- [Meeting notes](#)
- [Video](#)

2. [System building and analysis tools](#)

This session gave an overview of tools used to build systems, interconvert files, analyse data, etc. The main question covered in this session was identification of the challenges for such tools to be interoperable with (1) commonly used MD packages, (2) each other in a general workflow, where “workflow” can be used in its broadest definition, from a shell script to a graph executed on a workflow manager. Finding what approaches work and what are pertinent issues have been the main focus of the discussion, which led to an early discussion of file formats. Many analysis tools presented are able to work with different trajectory formats, however, creating/interconverting input files for different MD engines poses a much greater challenge. There was a strong consensus on the importance of semantics and well documented file formats, which has been characterized as a weak spot at the moment. There was a lot of murmur against PDB and problems arising from this file format, however, it has been recognized that moving away from PDB has proved to be a challenge due to its ubiquitous use and human readability. NetCDF was mentioned as a file format that can capture a lot of important simulation information. The general consensus is that finding a single format to satisfy different requirements and optimization challenges would be a tall order, which is why building common APIs have been recognized as a potentially the easiest (but not easy) path toward interoperability, while maintaining diversity of MD software ecosystem. This approach, or any other that would aim to build a common solution, will require collaboration and coordination of the major developer communities in the field.

- **Speakers:** Oliver Beckstein (chair), Wonpil Im, Alan Grossfield, Daniel Roe, Robert McGibbon, John Stone, Joshua Anderson
- [Meeting notes](#)
- [Video](#)

3. [Standardization of file format \(I/O\)](#)

The aim of this session was to provide insights into the current state of the existing software packages I/O approaches and what are the major obstacles for interoperability, as well as propose some solution frameworks. At the moment, lack of clear specifications for many file formats, or (mis)use and variations between different implementations of the same formats, are some of the main causes of the interoperability headaches in the field. However, the field is also

facing some new challenges due to ever increasing computing power, generation of larger and larger datasets, advanced visualization requirements (real time, VR), etc., which affect I/O management requirements (compression, specific data organization, ...). However, these new developments also provide an opportunity to learn from the past experiences, good and bad, and potentially join different efforts to accelerate development and adoption of new file formats, where improving user experience is one of the main goals.

This was one of the most challenging discussions, but it has been re-iterated that standardization of the input file formats pose a greater challenge than agreeing on the standard output format. Again, paying more attention to semantics has been recognized as a key to interoperability, combined with the use of APIs. It has been noted that community processes for discussing standards and reaching mutual agreement are lacking, often resulting with a file format proliferation. This topic will require ongoing communication in virtual and real space between developers of major MD packages. Some suggestions were made regarding the next possible steps, mostly focused on standardizing a trajectory format based on the existing TNG format as a potential seed for community collaboration. The rationale behind this suggestion is its near-complete status, where the remaining 10% of work could be done in collaboration with other MD communities on the path to a standard file format. This discussion also resulted with a broad specification of information which should be contained by a [general trajectory file format](#) with semantic versioning enabled. Standardization of input files and a common system object is likely to require more effort, but enthusiasm to work on this topic has been expressed by a number of attendees.

- **Speakers:** Jean-Philip Piquemal, Joao Ribeiro, Erik Lindahl, Peter Eastman, Jason Swails, Bradley Dice
- [Meeting notes](#)
- [Video](#)

4. [Reproducible calculations of properties / Workflows](#)

Estimation and prediction of various chemical and physical properties for a given molecular system is one of the key applications of computational chemistry methods, including molecular dynamics. As in any other computational discipline, reproducibility of different MD calculations will be affected by hardware, software, and human factors. For example, running the same type of calculation on the same system in different software packages resulted in (slightly) different results, regardless of the amount of tweaking to counter any known sources of errors, as demonstrated by a couple of speakers. Identifying the sources of possible errors can be a very complex task, and reproducibility is additionally challenged by poor documentation of calculation protocols and system building steps. Often, there are many different ways to perform the same task and many details are skipped in describing steps and methods in system preparation and calculation setup, making certain calculations difficult or impossible to reproduce.

Discussion in this session further focused on how we could validate our methods and results in a more robust and systematic way. One part of this problem is related to the correct application of different methods and models to compute properties, while the other part of the challenge is about selecting appropriate experimental data or other computational results for valid comparison. A set of “best practices” articles was suggested as a welcome resource for the community. These include how to compute different properties and how to report results, and some guidelines for molecular simulation software development in this context. Again, data sharing has been mentioned as an important component of reproducible research. Implementation of some simple tests included in different simulation packages by default to ensure consistent results for computed energies has also been suggested.

- **Speakers:** David Mobley (chair), Michael Shirts, Levi Naden, Julien Michel, Lillian Chong, Max Bonomi

- [Meeting notes](#)
- [Video](#)

Recommended actions

Due to the discussion overlap between the topics covered in the Sessions 1 and 4, and Sessions 2 and 3, the recommended short and long term actions have been aggregated in two major topics for a clearer overview:

1. Data sharing and reproducibility
2. Simulation I/O and file formats

1. Data sharing and reproducibility

Immediate actions:

- Identify and create a list of the existing repositories where different data can be stored and shared when submitting a publication or just when sharing data on its own. This list can take the form of a Github repository, a Google sheet, or similar shared resource able to support multiple editors and contributors.

Note: *The recent developments related to sharing modelling results to better understand protein targets from SARS-COV-2 coronavirus led by both MolSSI and Bioexcel (<https://github.com/MolSSI/covid> , <https://covid.molssi.org>) are already following the recommendations discussed during this workshop.*

- Establish best practices for property calculations, or consolidate efforts with the existing recommendations for “simple” property calculations for pure systems, hydration free energies and protein-ligand free energies.
- Establish a list of things we should NOT do in molecular simulation. For example, compare results to raw experimental data rather than derived values, or validate our methods solely with how close the result is to an experimental or experimentally derived value.
 - Define a list of properties to use for comparisons.

Long term solutions:

- Create a community to define standards and develop best practices around data and code sharing with publications and specify expectations for authors, editors and reviewers. This can be summarized in an article, possible LiveCoMS, or posted at any appropriate site.
- Ask software packages to enable automatic generation of metadata files associated with each simulation run and capture information about simulation parameters, software and hardware for easier provenance tracking, data sharing and reproducibility purposes.
- Implement a comparison of physical properties across codes (test example included with software distribution packages) to potentially include examples of a “simple” calculation, hydration free energies and protein-ligand binding free energies.
- Create a repository for (I/O) simulation data that have a high re-use potential (for example, very long simulations, important systems, etc). This will require definition of the high re-use potential dataset selection criteria.

- Incentivize researchers to share their data through making it easy and rewarding by providing suitable infrastructure, and through institutional policies (funding agencies, journals and editors, universities, etc).
- Develop and maintain best practices/recommendations for molecular simulation software development in a collaborative, ongoing process.

2. Simulation I/O and file formats

Immediate actions:

- Start a repository with a detailed documentation of the existing and future file formats and parsers. List all known specifications and implementation flavours for each format known today.
- Immediately update all examples and tutorials to replace PDB with PDBx or MMCIF in an effort to move the field away from using (different implementations of) PDB files.
- Start experimenting

Long term solutions:

- Build collaborative and inclusive processes that support consensus building around infrastructure components of common interest
- Moving toward common APIs to ensure interoperability while maintaining diversity of MD software ecosystem.
- Clear and unambiguous definition of formats and underlying semantics, i.e. what content is in which files (bond orders, partial charges, etc).
- Input file standardization has been recognized as a major challenge, much more so than standardization of output files. Some existing solutions (for example, [DESRES MSYS](#)) could be used as a starting point for development of a common system preparation solution.
- Build a common (standard) trajectory format around TNG, which is almost complete, as a pilot project for multi-package, cross-community collaboration.
- Some proposed features of a more general format include:
 - Define an API for the reader (iterate until acceptable solution has been found)
 - Checksum on file in total (checksum blocks later)
 - Consideration of multiple challenges associated with this problem (information structure, access patterns, formats, backwards compatibility, nullability of the fields, uneven frame updates, etc.)
 - “General field” promotion to “standard field” strategy
 - Agreement between designers/implementers that you will implement this spec
 - Agreement between MD suites that you will use this as a default in future versions?

Actions taken

- Create a distributed, collaborative platform for all workshop participants and the wider community to continue discussion about interoperability issues and best practices in the field, and to establish working groups to collaborate and solve together some of the list problems. The

initial steps include opening up some communication channels under the name of *Molecular Modeling Open Source Software* (MMOSS):

- Procuring *mmoss.io* domain to create a simple website for easy information sharing and finding by the interested community members.
- Creating *mmoss-io* Slack channel for more efficient communication and information exchange about various topics discussed in the workshop and beyond.
- Creating *mmoss-io* account on Confluence for distributed project management.
- Creating *mmoss-io* organization on GitHub for collaborative software development and idea sharing.
- Creating *mmoss-io* account on Twitter to reach out to a wider audience in the field.

All these platforms were created with an intention to become a community resource. The accounts were created by Karmen Condic-Jurkic, who currently acts as an administrator, but admin privileges will be shared and transferred to other volunteers in the community. More activity and engagement is expected in the second half of 2020.

Further recommendations

- Organization of interoperability hackathon focused on a specific set of problems (funded by MolSSI and/or BioExcel).
- Funding MolSSI fellows whose primary responsibility will be to work on interoperable components and frameworks.
- Promotion of best practices in molecular dynamics simulations and incentives for sharing data and code.
- Infrastructure support for sharing data and code.